

On *o*-Nitrocinnamaldehyde

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This note deals with the observations made during the condensation of *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde with malonic, malonanilic, malon-*o*-,*m*- and *p*-toluidic and malon-*o*-chloranilic acids. A trace of an organic base like pyridine, piperidine or 2,4-lutidine, or of a salt like pyridine acetate or molecular proportions of glacial acetic acid was used in these experiments as a condensing agent.

Condensation with malonic acid furnished two products—one melting at 205° and the other at 216°. The latter was identified as *o*-nitrocinnamylidene-acetic acid. The lower melting product is taken to be *o*-nitrocinnamylidene-malonic acid, but this needs further confirmation. In all other cases only one type of product, viz., *o*-nitrocinnamylidene-malonanilic, -toluidic, or -chloranilic acid, was obtained. The other expected product, viz., *o*-nitrocinnamylidene-acetanilide, -toluidide, or -chloranilide, was not isolated in any reaction. This is in agreement with the observations made by Bagchi and Ittyerah (*Agra Univ. J. Res.*, 1954, 3, 143) in the reactions of cinnamaldehyde.

It was further noted that in all reactions, except with that of malonic acid, *o*-nitrocinnamaldehyde showed greater reactivity than the unsubstituted aldehyde. Mention may be made here that attempts to condense hydrocinnamaldehyde with the reactive methylene compounds, named before, were unsuccessful.

The general procedure involved the mixing of the aldehyde (1 *M*), acid (1*M*), and the catalyst (0.15 *M*) in a r.b. flask and heating the mixture at 100-105° for 4 hours. The solid left was extracted with a strong solution of sodium carbonate. The alkali extract on addition of excess of HCl gave the product, which could be further purified by recrystallisation from ethanol. When acetic acid was used as a condensing agent, it was added in molecular proportions. The two products obtained in malonic acid condensation could be separated by ether, *o*-nitrocinnamylideneacetic acid being soluble and the other component insoluble.

TABLE I

No.	Name.	Formula.	M.P.	%Yield.	%Nitrogen.	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	*X-acetic acid	C ₁₁ H ₉ O ₄ N	216°	64	6.11	6.39
2.	X-malonanilic acid	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ O ₆ N ₂	185°	89	8.83	8.29
3.	X-malon- <i>o</i> -toluidic acid	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₂	217°	51	8.10	7.95
4.	X-malon- <i>m</i> -toluidic acid	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₂	212°	56	7.87	7.95
5.	X-malon- <i>p</i> -toluidic acid	C ₁₉ H ₁₅ O ₆ N ₂	225°	86	8.4	7.95
6.	X-malon- <i>o</i> -chloroanilic acid	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ O ₆ N ₂ Cl	228°	67	7.78	7.66

*X-stands for *o*-nitrocinnamylidene.